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We have reached a decision regarding your manuscript submission to **Journal of Neonatal Surgery** titled as – “Closed Reduction and Casting for a Gartland Type IIB Supracondylar Humerus Fracture in a Child: A Case Report”

Our Decision is to: **Accept Submission**

Journal of Neonatal Surgery

Mohamed Samy Elharoun

Our Indexing Partner's

